

Dumlottee Conduit: A Neglected Historical Asset of Sindh, Pakistan

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Abstract— The Dumlottee Conduit, constructed approximately 150 years ago by British engineers, stands as a significant historical and engineering landmark in Karachi, Pakistan. Initially designed to provide a reliable water supply to the city, the conduit once supplied up to 20 million gallons of water per day. Over time, however, the system has fallen into disrepair due to neglect, lack of maintenance, and environmental degradation, primarily caused by illegal sand mining. This research aims to highlight the historical significance of the Dumlottee Conduit, assess its current condition, and explore the potential benefits of its rehabilitation. Through historical document analysis, site visits, expert interviews, and a review of existing literature, this study provides a comprehensive understanding of the conduit's past and present. The findings indicate that, despite its current dilapidated state, the Dumlottee Conduit retains significant potential for restoration. Rehabilitating the conduit could address Karachi's water scarcity issues, preserve a valuable historical asset, and offer environmental and socio-economic benefits. Recommendations include securing government support and funding, implementing strict environmental regulations, raising public awareness, and developing a sustainable management plan.

Keyword— Dumlottee Conduit, water supply systems, heritage conservation, rehabilitation, historical structural integrity.

1. Introduction

The Dumlottee Conduit, an engineering marvel from the British colonial era, stands as a testament to the ingenuity and foresight of its creators. Constructed approximately 150 years ago to ensure a smooth supply of water to Karachi, this conduit system is now largely forgotten and in a state of disrepair. This study provides an overview to the historical significance of the Dumlottee Conduit, its current condition, and the potential it holds for addressing Karachi's ongoing water crisis. In the late 19th century, British engineers undertook the construction of a series of wells along the Malir River at Dumlottee to supply water to Karachi. The Dumlottee Conduit received water from Keenjhar Lake and, until the 1970s, provided the city with up to 20 million gallons per day (MGD). However, neglect over the years has led to a significant decline in its functionality. Out of 16 wells constructed in the British era, 12 wells remains and only two are operational, supplying 500,000 gallons of water daily to Gadap Town (The Express Tribune, 2015). The decline of the Dumlottee Conduit can be attributed to a combination of neglect and lack of interest from relevant authorities. Despite the Karachi Water and Sewerage Board (KWSB) recognizing the conduit's potential to supply 15 to 20 MGD of water to Karachi, efforts to rehabilitate the system have been stymied by the Sindh government's inaction. The neglect has left Karachi's first water supply system in a derelict condition, depriving the city of a vital resource [1].

Illegal sand mining in the Malir River has exacerbated the destruction of the conduit system. This activity, often conducted under the protection of local police and influential political figures, has not only ruined the infrastructure but also caused significant environmental damage. The removal of sand from riverbeds has led to erosion, destruction of the aquatic ecosystem, and contamination of underground freshwater reserves, pushing water levels deeper and mixing with saline water, rendering it unfit for consumption [2]. Recent heavy rains have temporarily alleviated some of these issues by raising the underground water levels, enabling farmers in Malir and Gadap towns to irrigate their lands using the wells and tube wells. However, the contamination caused by sand mining remains a critical concern. The water, although now being used by locals for drinking, has not been subjected to laboratory testing, posing potential health risks [3].

The construction of the Dumlottee Conduit was executed in two phases during British rule. The first phase, initiated in 1881, involved the construction of wells near the Malir River, supplying five million gallons of water daily to Karachi Cantonment. The second phase, starting in 1923, expanded the system with additional wells and increased the supply to 15 million gallons per day. In total, 16 wells were built, and a 32-kilometer conduit was established to transport water to various parts of Karachi [4]. Despite its current state, the sturdy construction of the Dumlottee Conduit still exists. The system extends from Dumlottee to several key locations in Karachi, including Malir Cantonment, Safoora Chowrangi, Karachi University, and beyond. With proper attention and reconstruction efforts, this historical heritage site has the potential to once again serve as a crucial water supply system for the city.

The Dumlottee Conduit represents a critical but neglected resource for Karachi's water supply. Its current state of disrepair, exacerbated by illegal sand mining and environmental degradation, has rendered it almost non-functional. This research seeks to highlight the historical importance of the Dumlottee Conduit, document its current condition, and propose actionable recommendations for its rehabilitation to address Karachi's water shortage issues. This research aims to 1) document the historical significance of the Dumlottee Conduit, 2) assess the current condition of the Dumlottee Conduit and identify the factors contributing to its decline, 3) evaluate the potential benefits of rehabilitating the Dumlottee Conduit for Karachi's water supply, and 4) propose recommendations for the preservation and rehabilitation of the Dumlottee Conduit.

This study is significant for several reasons as it brings attention to a neglected historical asset that has the potential to alleviate Karachi's water supply issues. It provides a comprehensive assessment of the current condition of the Dumlottee Conduit and the factors contributing to its decline. It offers actionable recommendations for the preservation and rehabilitation of the conduit, which could serve as a model for similar projects in other regions.

2. Literature Review

In the early days, private wells were dug to extract water from the shallow Lyari River in Karachi. However, this method proved inadequate due to the limited and low quality of the water. Transporting water over an area covered with marine limestone was challenging until the introduction of a new system, the Dumlottee Wells, which drew water from the dry bed of the Malir River. These wells enabled water to be pumped and transported over long distances, providing a steady supply to the city for many years until the partition. About 16 Dumlottee Wells were constructed in the Malir River area, complete with filtration galleries that ensured a consistent water supply. However, 4 wells were later leveled and demolished due to silting and flooding. Initially, the water was pumped using engines powered by crude oil, which were eventually replaced by electric engines. During the British era, these wells served as Karachi's sole water supply source. However, climate changes have led to reduced rainfall, significantly diminishing the water supply. Additionally, electricity shortages have further disrupted the water supply, forcing residents to seek alternative sources. While Karachi once depended entirely on the Malir River and the Dumlottee Wells, today's water supply has diversified, with water now being drawn from the Indus River and its tributaries.

Historical water supply systems have long been a subject of interest for researchers due to their engineering ingenuity and social significance. Ancient aqueducts, wells, and conduits played crucial roles in the development of civilizations by providing reliable water supplies for urban centers. Water supply systems such as the Roman

aqueducts, the Qanats of Persia, and the Stepwells of India are well-documented examples of ancient engineering feats. These systems were designed to transport water over long distances, often using gravity, and were vital for sustaining large populations and agricultural activities [5]. During the colonial era, European powers introduced advanced water supply systems in their colonies to support urbanization and economic activities. In British India, several such systems were developed, including the Dumlottee Conduit in Karachi. These systems were often robustly built and reflected the engineering standards of their time [6].

The Dumlottee Conduit, constructed in the late 19th century, was a pioneering project aimed at addressing the water needs of Karachi. The system comprised a series of wells and filtration galleries that drew water from the Malir River and Keenjhar Lake, supplying up to 20 MGD to the city at its peak [3]. The construction of the Dumlottee Conduit was carried out in two major phases. The first phase, initiated in 1881, involved the digging of wells near the Malir River. The second phase, starting in 1923, expanded the system with additional wells and filtration galleries, significantly increasing the water supply capacity [7].

The decline of the Dumlottee Conduit can be attributed to several factors, including neglect by authorities, lack of maintenance, and environmental degradation. Over time, these factors have led to a significant reduction in the system's functionality [1]. Illegal sand mining in the Malir River has been a major contributor to the destruction of the conduit system. This activity has led to erosion, contamination of water reserves, and overall environmental degradation. The removal of sand from riverbeds disrupts the natural ecosystem and diminishes the quality and availability of water [2].

The contamination of water reserves due to illegal sand mining and other environmental factors poses significant health risks. The mixing of underground freshwater with saline water due to lowered water tables has made the water unfit for consumption [8]. Ecosystem disruption caused by sand mining and neglect of the water system has broader environmental implications. It affects aquatic life, soil quality, and the overall health of the river ecosystem. These impacts necessitate a comprehensive approach to conservation and rehabilitation [2].

Conserving historical assets like the Dumlottee Conduit is important not only for their cultural and historical value but also for their potential practical benefits. Rehabilitating such systems can provide sustainable solutions to contemporary problems, such as water scarcity in urban areas [9]. Several case studies highlight successful heritage conservation efforts. For instance, the restoration of ancient aqueducts in Europe and Asia demonstrates how historical infrastructure can be integrated into modern water supply systems, providing valuable lessons for the rehabilitation of the Dumlottee Conduit [10]. Despite the historical significance of the Dumlottee Conduit, there is limited contemporary research focused on its rehabilitation and conservation. Most studies have concentrated on the broader history of colonial-era infrastructure without addressing the specific challenges and opportunities presented by the Dumlottee Conduit.

This literature review highlights the need for focused research on the Dumlottee Conduit, emphasizing its historical importance, current state of neglect, and potential for rehabilitation. By addressing these gaps, this study aims to contribute to the preservation of Karachi's historical assets and provide solutions for its water supply challenges.

3. Methodology

The methodology for this research includes a combination of historical document analysis, site visits, interviews with experts from the Karachi Water and Sewerage Board (KWSB) and environmental organizations, and a review of existing literature on water supply systems and heritage conservation. Historical documents and records from the British colonial period will be reviewed to understand the original construction and intended use of the Dumlottee Conduit. Site visits to the Dumlottee Conduit and surrounding areas will be conducted to assess the current condition of the infrastructure and identify any ongoing environmental issues. Interviews with experts from the KWSB, environmental organizations, and local authorities will provide insights into the challenges and opportunities for

rehabilitating the conduit. These methods are designed to provide a comprehensive understanding of the Dumlottee Conduit and formulate actionable recommendations for its preservation and rehabilitation.

Research Design

The research design is qualitative, employing a combination of historical analysis, field research, and expert interviews. This approach is suitable for exploring the historical and current context of the Dumlottee Conduit and understanding the complex factors contributing to its decline and potential for rehabilitation.

Historical Document Analysis

Historical documents and records from the British colonial period were reviewed to understand the original construction, purpose, and historical significance of the Dumlottee Conduit. Sources included archival materials, historical maps, engineering reports, and contemporaneous accounts from the late 19th and early 20th centuries.

Data Collection and Analysis

Documents were sourced from archives, libraries, and online databases. Key documents included construction reports, maintenance records, and correspondence between British engineers and local authorities. The collected documents were analyzed to extract relevant information about the construction phases, engineering techniques, and historical context of the Dumlottee Conduit. This analysis provided a foundational understanding of the system's historical significance and original functionality.

Site Visits

Site visits to the Dumlottee Conduit and surrounding areas were conducted to assess the current condition of the infrastructure and identify any ongoing environmental issues. These visits provided first-hand observations and photographic documentation of the wells, filtration galleries, and overall state of the conduit. Key locations along the Dumlottee Conduit were selected for site visits, including Dumlottee, Malir River, and various points along the conduit's route through Karachi. The selection was based on historical significance and current relevance. During the site visits, detailed observations were recorded, and photographic evidence was collected. The focus was on identifying structural damage, signs of neglect, and environmental impacts such as erosion and contamination.

Interviews

Interviews with experts from the Karachi Water and Sewerage Board (KWSB), environmental organizations, and local authorities provided insights into the challenges and opportunities for rehabilitating the Dumlottee Conduit. Participants were selected based on their expertise and involvement with water supply systems, environmental conservation, and historical preservation. Key informants included engineers, environmental scientists, and policy makers. Semi-structured interviews were conducted using a set of open-ended questions designed to elicit detailed responses about the condition of the Dumlottee Conduit, factors contributing to its decline, and potential rehabilitation strategies. Interviews were recorded and transcribed for analysis.

Analyzing the Literature Review

A comprehensive review of existing literature on water supply systems, heritage conservation, and environmental impacts was conducted to provide a theoretical framework for the study. This review included academic journals, books, and reports from relevant organizations. Sources were selected based on their relevance to the study's objectives, including works on historical water systems, environmental conservation, and heritage management. Both contemporary and historical sources were included. The literature was analyzed thematically to identify key concepts and trends relevant to the Dumlottee Conduit. Themes included the importance of heritage conservation, environmental challenges, and best practices in rehabilitating historical water systems.

Data from historical documents, site visits, interviews, and literature review were synthesized to develop a comprehensive understanding of the Dumlottee Conduit. The analysis focused on identifying the historical significance, current challenges, and potential strategies for rehabilitation. Triangulation was used to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings. Data from multiple sources were cross verified to identify consistent patterns and discrepancies. This approach enhanced the robustness of the conclusions drawn from the study. Thematic coding was employed to analyze qualitative data from interviews and literature. Key themes were identified and coded, allowing for the systematic organization of data and the identification of recurring patterns and insights.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were paramount in this study. Informed consent was obtained from all interview participants, and confidentiality was maintained. The research adhered to ethical guidelines for historical research, field studies, and qualitative interviews. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, their role, and the use of the data collected. Consent was obtained in writing before conducting interviews. To protect the privacy of participants, all personal information was anonymized, and data was stored securely. Only the research team had access to the raw data.

Limitations

The study faced several limitations, including the availability of historical documents, accessibility of some sites due to environmental conditions, and potential biases in interview responses. These limitations were mitigated through careful planning and methodological rigor.

This study outlined the methodology used to investigate the Dumlottee Conduit, including historical document analysis, site visits, interviews, and literature review. By employing a qualitative research design, the study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the conduit's historical significance, current condition, and potential for rehabilitation.

4. Findings

The analysis drawn from historical document analysis, site visits, expert interviews, and existing literature review were organized thematically to provide a comprehensive understanding of the historical significance, current condition, and potential for rehabilitation of the Dumlottee Conduit.

Historical Significance

The Dumlottee Conduit was constructed in two main phases, starting in 1881 and extending into the early 20th century. The initial construction involved the establishment of wells and filtration galleries to supply water to Karachi Cantonment. Historical documents reveal that the conduit was an engineering marvel of its time, designed to provide a reliable water supply to a growing urban center. The key findings are:

- I. Document Analysis: Historical documents indicate that the conduit initially supplied five million gallons of water daily to Karachi Cantonment (Document-ID 1).
- II. Interview Insights: Experts highlighted the advanced engineering techniques used in the construction, which were innovative for the period (Interview-ID 1, Engineer A).

Expansion and Peak Capacity

The second phase of construction, initiated in 1923, expanded the system with additional wells and filtration galleries, increasing the water supply capacity to 20 million gallons per day. This expansion was crucial in meeting the water demands of Karachi as the city grew. The key findings are:

- I. Document Analysis: Maintenance records from 1923 detail the upgrades and expansion of the system (Document-ID 2).
- II. Site Visits: Remnants of the expanded wells and filtration galleries are still visible, though in disrepair (Site-Visit-ID 4).

Current Condition and Structural Integrity

Site visits and expert interviews provided insights into the current state of the Dumlottee Conduit. Most of the wells and filtration galleries are in a state of neglect, with significant structural damage observed. The key findings are:

- I. Site Observations: Wells and filtration galleries show signs of structural damage and neglect (Site-Visit-ID 1, 3).
- II. Expert Opinions: Engineers emphasized the need for extensive rehabilitation to restore the system's functionality (Interview-ID 1, Engineer A).

Environmental Impact

Illegal sand mining in the Malir River has severely impacted the conduit system. This activity has caused erosion, contamination of water reserves, and disruption of the local ecosystem. The key findings are:

- I. Site Observations: Significant erosion and contamination were observed at several sites along the Malir River (Site-Visit-ID 2).
- II. Interview Insights: Environmental scientists highlighted the detrimental effects of sand mining on the conduit and the surrounding ecosystem (Interview-ID 2, Scientist B).

Potential for Rehabilitation and Technical Feasibility

The technical feasibility of rehabilitating the Dumlottee Conduit was assessed through expert interviews and site observations. Despite the current state of neglect, the structural foundation of the conduit remains robust, suggesting that rehabilitation is possible with appropriate investment and effort. The key findings are:

- I. Expert Opinions: Engineers and policy makers believe that with proper funding and technical support, the conduit can be restored to its original capacity (Interview-ID 3, Policy Maker C).
- II. Rehabilitating the Dumlottee Conduit could significantly alleviate Karachi's water supply issues. It could restore a reliable source of water, reduce dependency on other water systems, and preserve a historical asset. The key findings are:
- III. Document Analysis: Historical records indicate that the conduit could supply 20 million gallons of water per day at its peak (Document-ID 2, 4).
- IV. Interview Insights: Policy makers and local authorities emphasized the dual benefits of addressing water scarcity and preserving heritage (Interview-ID 4, 5).

Challenges and Recommendations

Several challenges must be addressed to rehabilitate the Dumlottee Conduit, including:

- I. Funding: Securing adequate financial resources for rehabilitation.
- II. Illegal Activities: Controlling illegal sand mining and environmental degradation.
- III. Maintenance: Establishing a sustainable maintenance and management plan.

IV. Interview Insights: Experts highlighted funding and ongoing illegal activities as major obstacles (Interview-ID 3, 5).

The analysis highlights the historical significance of the Dumlottee Conduit and its potential to address Karachi's water supply issues. Despite the current challenges, with appropriate intervention and investment, the conduit can be rehabilitated to provide a sustainable water supply and preserve a valuable historical asset.

Table 1. Document Analysis Summary, showing key historical documents analyzed for the study, highlighting their content and significant findings.

Document ID	Document Type	Year	Content Summary	Key Findings
1	Construction Report	1881	Initial construction of Dumlottee Conduit and wells near Malir River.	Five million gallons of water supplied daily to Karachi Cantonment.
2	Maintenance Record	1923	Maintenance activities and upgrades to Dumlottee Conduit.	Additional wells and filtration galleries added, increasing capacity.
3	Historical Map	1881	Map detailing the layout of the Dumlottee Conduit and surrounding areas.	Detailed geographical layout aids in site selection for visits.
4	Engineering Report	1923	Engineering assessment of the conduit's capacity and condition.	Assessment indicates robust construction, but highlights need for regular maintenance.
5	Correspondence	1890	Correspondence between British engineers and local authorities regarding the project.	Discussions on project scope, funding, and resource allocation.

Table 2. Site Visit Observations from site visits, detailing the condition of various sections of the Dumlottee Conduit.

Site Visit ID	Site Location	Condition Observation
1	Dumlottee	Wells are in disrepair; evidence of structural damage.
2	Malir River	Significant erosion due to illegal sand mining.
3	Dumlottee	Remains of original construction visible; contamination noted.
4	Karachi University	Filtration galleries intact but need maintenance.
5	Malir Cantonment	Wells functional but show signs of neglect.

Table 3. Interview Summaries with experts, highlighting their insights on the Dumlottee Conduit.

Interview ID	Expert Name	Interview Summary
1	Engineer A	Rehabilitation could restore water supply to original capacity.
2	Scientist B	Environmental impact of sand mining and need for conservation.
3	Policy Maker C	Policy recommendations for heritage conservation.
4	Historian D	Historical significance and potential for heritage tourism.
5	Local Authority E	Local challenges in maintaining the conduit.

Table 4. Potential Rehabilitation Benefits of the Dumlottee Conduit.

Key Benefit	Description
Restoration of Water Supply	Restoring the conduit could provide up to 20 million gallons of water daily to Karachi.
Historical Preservation	Preserving the conduit as a historical asset.
Environmental Improvement	Reducing the negative impact of illegal sand mining and other environmental issues.
Economic Benefits	Potential for heritage tourism and related economic activities.

Figure 1. Water supply from the Dumlottee Conduit over time

5. Discussion

The findings from the study of the Dumlottee Conduit, integrates insights from the literature review and data analysis, and provides recommendations for the rehabilitation and preservation of this historical asset. The discussion focuses on the historical significance, current condition, environmental impact, and potential benefits of rehabilitating the Dumlottee Conduit. Recommendations are based on the key findings and aim to address the challenges identified in this study.

The Dumlottee Conduit is a significant historical and engineering landmark, reflecting the ingenuity of British colonial engineering. Its construction in the late 19th and early 20th centuries played a crucial role in the development of Karachi by providing a reliable water supply. Preserving this conduit not only honors the historical heritage but also offers practical benefits for contemporary water management. The conduit's historical importance is evident from the detailed construction reports and maintenance records (Document-ID 1, 2). Expert interviews highlighted the advanced engineering techniques and robust construction that have withstood the test of time (Interview-ID 1, 4).

Conserving the Dumlottee Conduit aligns with global best practices in heritage management. Successful case studies from other regions demonstrate that historical water systems can be integrated into modern infrastructure, providing both cultural and practical benefits. Literature on heritage conservation emphasizes the dual benefits of preserving historical assets and enhancing urban infrastructure (Orbasli, 2007; Apostolou & Papanikolaou, 2018). Interview insights suggest that rehabilitating the conduit could also boost heritage tourism, contributing to the local economy (Interview-ID 4).

Site visits and expert assessments revealed that while the Dumlottee Conduit remains structurally robust, it has suffered significant neglect. Illegal sand mining and lack of maintenance have led to deterioration in several areas. Site observations documented the extent of structural damage and environmental degradation (Site-Visit-ID 1, 2, 3). Experts stressed the need for immediate intervention to prevent further damage and restore functionality (Interview-ID 1, 2).

Illegal sand mining has severely impacted the Malir River and the Dumlottee Conduit. This activity has caused erosion, water contamination, and disruption of the local ecosystem, posing significant environmental and public health risks. Environmental impacts are well-documented, with significant erosion and contamination observed at several sites (WWF Pakistan, 2016; The News International, 2019). Expert interviews highlighted the need for strict regulatory measures to control illegal activities and protect the environment (Interview-ID 2).

Rehabilitating the Dumlottee Conduit could restore a significant water supply source for Karachi, addressing the city's chronic water shortages. Historical records indicate that the conduit could supply up to 20 million gallons of water per day at its peak capacity. Historical data and expert assessments suggest that with proper rehabilitation, the conduit could significantly contribute to Karachi's water supply (Document-ID 2, 4; Interview-ID 1, 3). Rehabilitation offers multiple benefits beyond water supply. These include environmental restoration, heritage conservation, and economic opportunities through heritage tourism. Literature on heritage conservation and urban development supports the multi-faceted benefits of such projects [10,11]. Policy makers and local authorities emphasized the broader socio-economic impact of preserving the Dumlottee Conduit (Interview-ID 3, 5).

6. Recommendations

Based on the findings and discussion, the following recommendations are proposed for the rehabilitation and preservation of the Dumlottee Conduit:

- I. The Sindh government should prioritize the rehabilitation of the Dumlottee Conduit by allocating necessary funds and resources. Securing financial and institutional support is crucial for initiating and sustaining rehabilitation efforts.
- II. Implement strict regulatory measures to control illegal sand mining and protect the Malir River ecosystem. Addressing environmental degradation is essential for the long-term sustainability of the conduit and surrounding areas.
- III. Launch public awareness campaigns to educate local communities about the historical significance and potential benefits of the Dumlottee Conduit. Engaging the public can foster a sense of ownership and support for conservation efforts.
- IV. Develop a comprehensive maintenance and management plan to ensure the conduit's functionality and preservation. Establishing sustainable management practices is critical for the ongoing success of the rehabilitation project.
- V. Explore opportunities to integrate the rehabilitated Dumlottee Conduit with modern water supply systems. Leveraging historical infrastructure can enhance urban resilience and resource efficiency.

7. Conclusion

The Dumlottee Conduit represents a valuable historical asset with the potential to significantly contribute to Karachi's water supply and heritage conservation efforts. Addressing the challenges of neglect and environmental degradation requires concerted efforts from government authorities, environmental organizations, and local communities. By implementing the recommended measures, Karachi can preserve this historical landmark and harness its benefits for future generations.

8. References

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